

The Role of Project method in EFL for Pre-intermediate Students

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Abstract

This article highlights the significance of project-based learning in English education, exploring its positive impact on student engagement and overall language development. Based on research, project work demonstrates several benefits, including: increased Student Motivation: Project-based learning fosters a sense of purpose and ownership, motivating students to actively participate in the learning process. Integration of Language Skills: Projects seamlessly integrate all four language skills (reading, writing, speaking, and listening) and contribute to a holistic development of linguistic competence.

Key words: *project method, pupils, motivation, innovative, pedagogy. English.*

Introduction

The rapid development of Uzbekistan necessitates the integration of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies (ICT) into the education system. This is especially crucial for foreign language teaching, where innovative approaches are key to enhancing learning outcomes.

In this article, it's essential to refine the methodology for implementing project-based learning within English language classrooms.

English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction for pre-intermediate students presents unique challenges and opportunities. Educators increasingly turn to project technology as a powerful tool to enhance learning outcomes in this critical stage of language acquisition. Integrating project technology not only engages pre-intermediate students but also cultivates essential skills necessary for their linguistic development and future success in a globalized world.

Literature review

Innovation is a defining characteristic of the contemporary education system. It's driven by the pedagogical staff's readiness and expertise in embracing

new methods, coupled with their ability to apply creative strategies in their daily teaching practices. This ultimately determines the quality and effectiveness of the educational process. The didactic scientists of our country: O. Rozikov, N. Saidahmedov, M. Usmonboyeva, Z. Matyakubova, B. Kulmatov are designing the educational process, applying educational technologies to the teaching process of special subjects, as well as determining the effectiveness of educational technology. and conducted research on issues such as evaluation.

Project-based learning is a common approach in our school to help students apply and integrate knowledge and skills related to their studies. We view projects as creative endeavors that align with a student's individual abilities and developmental stage, ensuring they meet the standards set by the curriculum. This methodology has been extensively studied and championed by prominent educators and researchers like Legutke, Thomas, Heines, Brumfit, Hutchinson, Fried-Booth, and others.

Methodology

For pre-intermediate EFL students, maintaining engagement and motivation is crucial. Project technology offers a variety of interactive and multimedia tools that cater to different learning styles. Platforms like interactive whiteboards, educational apps, and digital storytelling tools can transform traditional lessons into dynamic, hands-on experiences. These technologies allow students to actively participate in their learning process, which enhances their motivation to improve language skills.

Project-based learning (PBL) through technology provides pre-intermediate students with opportunities to use English in authentic contexts. Tasks such as creating multimedia presentations, conducting virtual interviews, or collaborating on digital projects require students to communicate effectively in English. This practical application of language skills not only reinforces vocabulary and grammar but also builds confidence in using English for real-world purposes.

Discussion

In today's digital age, proficiency in digital literacy is as important as language proficiency. Project technology introduces pre-intermediate EFL students to digital tools and platforms, nurturing their digital literacy skills. Whether navigating online resources, researching information, or producing digital content, students learn to critically evaluate and utilize technology to enhance their learning experience. These skills are essential for their academic and professional growth in an increasingly digitalized society.

Collaborative projects facilitated by technology encourage pre-intermediate EFL students to work together to solve problems and achieve common goals. Through group discussions, online forums, or virtual teamwork, students practice collaboration, negotiation, and conflict resolution skills—all while improving their English language proficiency. Such activities foster critical thinking as students analyze information, evaluate ideas, and make decisions collectively, preparing them for future academic and professional challenges.

Project technology enables pre-intermediate EFL students to connect with peers from different cultural backgrounds globally. Virtual exchanges, joint projects with international classrooms, or digital pen-pal programs expose students to diverse perspectives and practices. These interactions promote intercultural understanding, empathy, and respect, essential qualities in a globalized world. Moreover, students learn to communicate effectively across cultural boundaries, preparing them for future international academic and professional endeavors.

In conclusion, project technology plays a crucial role in enhancing EFL instruction for pre-intermediate students by providing engaging, authentic, and interactive learning experiences. By integrating digital tools and platforms into the curriculum, educators can effectively support students' language development, digital literacy, collaborative skills, critical thinking, and intercultural competence. As technology continues to evolve, its integration into EFL education for pre-intermediate learners will remain instrumental in preparing them to thrive in an interconnected and multicultural world. Embracing project technology empowers educators to foster a dynamic and enriching learning environment where pre-

intermediate EFL students can achieve linguistic proficiency and global competence.

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